

Hasselt University CoARA action plan (2023-2027)

As part of its commitment to fostering a culture of responsible research assessment, Hasselt University has endorsed the principles outlined in the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. This commitment is driven by the recognition that traditional assessment models often rely too heavily on narrow quantitative indicators, which can act as a barrier to capture the wide variety of academic contributions.

To address this imbalance, we envision a transition toward an assessment culture where qualitative excellence, integrity, and diverse impact are central, complemented by a balanced application of quantitative indicators. In this framework, we advocate for the responsible use of metrics, hence moving away from metrics as a primary filter toward a system where quantitative data never stand in isolation, but serve as a supporting tool for qualitative expert judgment. By acknowledging context sensitivity and ensuring transparency through a diverse set of indicators, we aim to capture the variety of research performance.

This action plan details the steps required to achieve this shift, ranging from establishing transparent career paths to providing professional support for researchers at all stages. Our strategy focuses on reinforcing existing initiatives while introducing new actions to further integrate these core values into our institutional fabric. By doing so, Hasselt University seeks to empower its researchers and contribute to an overarching culture of responsible assessment that rewards quality and openness. In sharing this plan, we aim to contribute to collective learning and awareness within the CoARA community and beyond.

1. Overview of actions

	Actions	Deadline
1	Develop transparent career paths for academic staff.	End of 2026
2	Conduct a scientific synthesis and create a vision paper on societal impact.	End of 2026
3	Provide training opportunities for early-career researchers.	Continuous
4	Establish a framework for the responsible use of metrics in research assessment.	End of 2027
5	Update and monitor doctoral regulations, procedures and criteria.	Continuous
6	Identify and analyse training needs regarding open science, research data management, FAIR -principles, RRI, ethical aspects of publishing and peer review.	Continuous
7	Leverage networks like Eureka-Pro and explore opportunities for job shadowing.	Continuous
8	Report progress on the action plan to the Research Council and the Board of Governors.	Continuous
9	Share key updates and relevant documentation on the UHasselT website.	Continuous
10	Publish CoARA action plan on Zenodo.	End of 2026

2. Overview of prospective actions per commitment

	Commitment CoARA	State of play	Objectives and actions	Key responsible(s)	Timeline
1.	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research	<p>Through its 2022-2026 Research & Innovation policy, Hasselt University implements a differentiated career policy to overcome the limitations of traditional assessment models that disproportionately rely on a narrow set of bibliometric outputs. Key examples of this implementation include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Since 2024, the academic file, an electronic portfolio for researchers, includes a variety of academic output such as media engagement, advisory board participation, and political or societal input, addressing the historical invisibility of these in formal evaluations. - An internal working group on societal impact is currently mapping a structural embedding of social valorisation. This initiative aims to bridge the gap between the university's strategic focus on 	<p>To remove systemic barriers, we are committed to the following objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A project was initiated to develop and define clear career paths for academic staff, establishing specific expectations for each academic level, Assistant Professor, Associate Professor, and Full Professor across three key areas: teaching, research, and impact. A key aim of the project is to determine how diversity in research outputs can be acknowledged and included within academic career assessment. It will also assess methods for achieving responsible and balanced research evaluation. This ensures that diverse outputs are translated into formalized promotion criteria, resolving current ambiguity in career progression. - The ongoing analysis of the working group on societal impact will culminate in a scientific synthesis and vision paper at the end of 2026, containing recommendations concerning e.g., the 	<p>Career paths - partim research evaluation: Rectorate and Information management and strategic data analysis Unit, Directorate OBI</p> <p>Societal impact paper: Rectoral delegate</p> <p>Doctoral schools, Team PhD and Responsible Research Integrity Unit, Directorate OBI</p>	End of 2026

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		<p>impact and the absence of standardized criteria to reward such efforts.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research institutes are increasingly evaluated based on their contribution to societal challenges, while individual evaluation criteria are updated to formally include research valorization. <p>The 2017 competency overview for PhD holders provides structured definitions and assessment tools to recognise a broad set of skills and outcomes. In addition, the Doctoral Schools develop and support initiatives for science communication, ethics and research management. This ensures that PhD candidates develop into internationally oriented research professionals who are broadly employable, both in and outside the academic sector.</p>	<p>organisational and evaluation model of UHasselt.</p> <p>The competency overview for PhD holders allows the Doctoral Schools to continuously refine their training offer. By identifying specific needs and competences (such as collaboration within research teams, communication, ...) and academic skills (e.g., ethics, IP, statistics, ...) we ensure that early-career researchers are prepared for a broad range of career opportunities available to doctorate holders.</p>		Continuous

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2.	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators	<p>While Flemish government funding (BOF and IOF) is still largely allocated based on quantitative metrics, Hasselt University recognizes that an over-reliance on numerical output can overshadow the intrinsic quality of research. Therefore, Hasselt University is implementing a more nuanced evaluation framework that prioritizes the synergy between qualitative peer review and quantitative indicators.</p> <p>This commitment is already visible in several procedures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In BOF funding procedures traditional metrics are supplemented by qualitative evidence. For BOF large projects the assessment involves standard assessment of the research proposal, along with a narrative component that details the socio-economic impact and dissemination strategies. Similarly, PhD mandate applications allow candidates to provide a personal statement, providing 	<p>To translate this qualitative vision into structural career progression, a project was initiated to develop and define clear expectations for Assistant to Full Professors across teaching, research, and impact. This project directly addresses the challenge of acknowledging diverse outputs within formal assessments, ensuring they are translated into formalized promotion criteria by the end of 2026 (See also commitment 1).</p> <p>Furthermore, the transition toward qualitative evaluation will be strengthened by the recommendations from the working group on societal impact. It should be expected that their findings will provide the necessary framework to better value diverse forms of impact within recruitment and promotion tracks (See also commitment 1).</p>	<p>Rectorate</p> <p>Internal Research Policy Unit, Directorate OBI</p>	End of 2026

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		<p>essential context to justify potential gaps in quantitative records that standard metrics often fail to explain.</p> <p>For institutional assessment, Hasselt University employs a multi-layered peer-review process. The Research Council, supported by an external Strategic Advisory Board, evaluates the strategic plans of institutes. Composed of external experts within the relevant scientific fields, the Strategic Advisory Board assesses the presented strategic vision. This formal evaluation is complemented by an institute-specific Scientific Advisory Boards. Consisting of external members, these boards serve as internal sounding boards, providing ongoing strategic advice and support in both the execution of current plans and the drafting of new institutional visions.</p>			
3.	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and	As outlined in the Research Policy & Innovation Policy Plan (2022-2026), Hasselt University is transitioning away from a narrow reliance on journal-based metrics,	To institutionalize responsible assessment and overcome remaining metric-reliance, the university will:	Rectorate Information management and strategic data	End of 2027

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	publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index	<p>to address the risk that prestige-based indicators, such as the JIF, are used as a proxy for individual research quality. This is evidenced in several initiatives, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The 2024 expansion of the academic portfolio captures societal impact and policy advice, reducing the disproportionate weight of traditional citation indices. <p>As noted in Commitment 2, BOF funding procedures now utilize narrative components to contextualize quantitative data.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - draft a policy on the responsible use of metrics to provide evaluators with clear criteria on what constitutes appropriate and inappropriate indicator use. This policy will be communicated internally and will be made accessible on our website by the end of 2026. - operationalize this policy through updated guidelines and procedures for the evaluation of researchers, institutes, and funding applications from 2027 onwards to ensure structural embedment at all levels of assessment. 	<p>analysis Unit, Directorate OBI</p> <p>Internal Research Policy Unit, Directorate OBI</p>	
4.	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment	Hasselt University maintains a critical and nuanced stance toward international rankings. While the university monitors these rankings for external benchmarking and international visibility on its website, they are strictly excluded from internal evaluation procedures and funding allocations. Consequently, no further policy actions are deemed necessary for the 2023-2027 period, as the principle of non-		Information management and strategic data analysis Unit, Directorate OBI	

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		reliance is already firmly embedded in institutional practice.			
5.	Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to	<p>Hasselt University is investing in digital transformation and IT infrastructure to support organisational changes required for a reformed approach to research assessment. These investments aim to facilitate data-driven decision-making, streamline processes, and enhance transparency.</p> <p>Our collaboration with the Flanders Research Information Space (FRIS, https://researchportal.be/en) and collaborations with ECOOM ensures alignment with regional policy frameworks and enhances the quality and comparability of our research data. This integrated digital environment ensures that quantitative tools are based on high-quality data that support qualitative expert judgment by providing evaluators with high-quality, verified information.</p>	<p>To bridge the gap between policy ambitions and operational reality, UHasselt is committed to providing the necessary digital infrastructure and administrative support to facilitate a more holistic and differentiated assessment framework:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We will evolve our digital environment to ensure that "diversity in contributions" is not just a concept, but a measurable reality in researcher evaluations. We will expand the digital academic portfolio (see Commitment 1) to systematically capture non-traditional outputs, such as societal impact, open science practices. In addition, we will provide training and guidelines for researchers on how to interpret and use these new outputs to build a narrative-supporting evidence base for their assessments. - We will invest in the technical and operational integration of our core administrative systems. Specifically, we will complete the 	Rectorate, Information management and strategic data analysis Unit, Directorate OBI	

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			<p>synchronization between the Current Research Information System (CRIS), the HR database, and the financial system. This integration will culminate in the launch of a dedicated Business Intelligence dashboard designed for assessment committees. This tool will empower evaluators to automatically view research outputs in direct relation to a researcher's available time (FTE) and the specific project resources at their disposal.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We will ensure that our digital investments serve to support, rather than replace, expert qualitative peer review by presenting quantitative metrics always alongside the researcher's career stage and specific constraints. 		
6.	Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes	<p>Hasselt University's 2022-2026 Research and Innovation Policy Plan outlines ongoing efforts to review and enhance research assessment criteria, tools, and processes.</p> <p>To foster broad institutional support for these endeavours, we</p>	The university is developing a framework for the responsible use of quantitative indicators in research assessment. This initiative also provides guidelines and training modules that empower researchers to construct evidence-based CVs. These resources will be aligned with international standards and the latest	Framework for the responsible use of quantitative indicators: Information management and strategic data	End of 2026

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<p>6.1 CRITERIA FOR UNITS AND INSTITUTIONS</p> <p>With the direct involvement of research organisations and researchers at all career stages, review and develop criteria for assessing research units and research</p>	<p>ensure a wide representation of relevant stakeholders in all processes related to our transition to a more qualitative assessment.</p> <p>6.1. Criteria for units and institutions</p> <p>For research institutes and centers, a strategic plan, including an HR strategy, is assessed throughout a 5-year period (including advice from external sounding boards). They are discussed during bilateral meetings with the research policy</p>	<p>findings from CoARA working groups and related initiatives, such as GraspOS. Furthermore, the university will implement the use of field-normalized indicators, such as Field Normalized Citation Impact, to ensure that the evaluation of research units is conducted within the appropriate disciplinary context. To guarantee transparency and accessibility, all criteria and supporting guidelines will be made publicly available via the university website.</p> <p>These criteria will be made publicly available via the UHasselt website.</p> <p>In parallel, efforts are being made to broaden the evaluation of research units, allowing for greater diversity in research profiles and contributions. In this context, the recommendations from the working group on societal impact should be expected to play an important role. By operationalizing their recommendations, we aim to refine the evaluation models for research units, ensuring that diverse forms of impact are recognized as core institutional achievements. This shift is</p>	<p>analysis Unit, Directorate OBI</p> <p>Internal Research Policy Unit, Directorate OBI</p> <p>Trainings: Internal Research Policy Unit and PhD and Responsible Research Integrity Unit, Directorate OBI</p> <p>Doctoral School Boards: Requirements</p> <p>Doctoral Regulations: PhD and Responsible Research Integrity Unit, Directorate OBI</p>	

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	<p>performing organisations, while promoting interoperability</p> <p>6.2 CRITERIA FOR PROJECTS AND RESEARCHERS</p> <p>With the direct involvement of researchers at all career stages, review and develop criteria, tools and processes for the assessment of research projects, research teams and researchers that are adapted to their context of application</p>	<p>director and vice-rector, allowing for contextual justification.</p> <p>6.2. Criteria for projects and researchers</p> <p>In specific programmes (e.g. BOF ZAP) there are additional (eligibility) criteria on the level of the researcher or team that must be met:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In case of a BOF ZAP, a dedicated BOF ZAP committee is installed as a sounding board that follows the professor throughout a 5- to 10-year trajectory, evaluating their integration into the institute, their supervision of PhD candidates, and their recognition within the international research community. - The assessment for BOF tenure-track positions is handled by specific BOF tenure-track commissions coordinated by the rectorate 	<p>closely linked to the career progression objectives under Commitment 1.</p> <p>The Doctoral School Boards monitor and update the requirements used in doctoral training to guarantee their relevance and alignment with evolving standards in the assessment of PhD candidates.</p> <p>The doctoral regulations and procedures are regularly updated, in consultation with our researchers. This collaborative approach ensures our processes are practical and responsive to the needs of our academic community. Our core objective is to make the doctoral process transparent to all stakeholders involved. While a monitoring system for the doctoral process is in place, it currently lacks the flexibility to fully capture the complexity of the PhD trajectory. Depending on resources, we will refine this system to ensure it meets our evolving needs and supports all stakeholders in a transparent manner.</p>		<p>End of 2026</p> <p>Continuous</p>

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		<p>and linked to the general ZAP-assessments and regulations, but with an additional focus on research criteria.</p> <p>At UHasselt, the doctoral schools are committed to fostering a dynamic and transparent environment for PhD candidates. The doctoral schools actively shape their programme by involving all key stakeholders (e.g., supervisors and PhD candidates) in defining the minimal requirements. Each doctoral school operates under the guidance of a Doctoral School Board which consists of representatives from diverse research domains, PhD candidates and postdoctoral researchers, ensuring a broad and inclusive perspective.</p> <p>All doctoral schools have minimal requirements related to science communication (outreach), valorisation, ethics & research integrity, research management (e.g. RDM, open science) and career & personal development,</p>			Continuous

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		<p>ensuring that the assessment includes the researcher's broader professional development and acquisition of transferable skills.</p> <p>According to the doctoral regulations, each PhD candidate should organize an annual progress meeting with their doctoral committee. A formal evaluation takes place every two years. This systematic follow-up assesses not only research progress but also the candidate's development against the doctoral school's minimal requirements and their broader competency development.</p>			
7.	Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use	Hasselt University is committed to raising awareness about responsible research assessment practices among its academic community. Evaluation criteria are transparently communicated to staff via the university's intranet, where staff can consult the principles and procedures used in internal evaluations. The evaluation criteria for BOF funding are available to researchers via	<p>Within the framework of CoARA, Hasselt University will continue to identify and analyse the needs for training or information sessions regarding open science, research data management, FAIR-principles, RRI, the ethical aspects of publishing and peer review.</p> <p>Appropriate frameworks for evaluators will be established, leveraging input and</p>	Training: University Library Unit, PhD and Responsible Research Integrity Unit, Directorate OBI	Continuous

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		<p>the university intranet, ensuring transparency and accessibility of assessment procedures.</p> <p>In addition, training initiatives offered through the Career Center and the Doctoral Schools help familiarise researchers with assessment processes and expectations throughout their career.</p> <p>The university actively engages in national and European working groups, including the VLIR working group on researcher evaluation, the CoARA working group, the EU Framework Programme, and the GraspOS initiative, to promote transparency, share best practices, and contribute to the development of common frameworks that support a level playing field in research assessment.</p>	<p>outcomes from the initiatives specified in commitment 1.</p>		

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8.	Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition	Hasselt takes on an active role on multiple levels (Flemish, national and international) in advocating the importance of committing resources to reforming research assessment. Hasselt University engages in the exchange of practices and experiences related to responsible research assessment through its participation in national and international networks. At the Flemish level, UHasselt contributes to relevant working groups coordinated by the Flemish Interuniversity Council (VLIR) and the Flemish Open Science Board. Internationally, Hasselt University leverages its ASTP membership to exchange best practices on the qualitative assessment of knowledge valorisation and societal impact, ensuring our evaluation methods align with broader European trends. These platforms offer opportunities to learn from peers, explore innovative approaches, and contribute to shaping shared practices. This external alignment is essential to prevent fragmented assessment standards and	To promote mutual learning, Hasselt University will leverage its participation in networks like Eureca-Pro and explore opportunities for job shadowing at other institutions to exchange best practices and experiences.	Everyone involved in these networks.	Continuous

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		<p>ensures that our institutional reforms remain compatible with regional and international career mobility.</p> <p>In addition, UHasselt will report on the progress of its action plan to the Research Council and the Board of Governors, and will communicate key developments to the broader research community via a dedicated webpage. The action plan will be made publicly available and updated annually to reflect progress and new insights. This commitment to public reporting addresses the current need for accountability and ensures that the transition to a new assessment culture remains transparent for all stakeholders.</p>			
9.	Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments		Hasselt University is committed to ensuring transparency in the implementation of its CoARA action plan. Progress on the action plan will be reported regularly to the Research Council and the Board of Governors.		continuous

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			To engage the broader research community, key updates and relevant documentation will be shared through a dedicated webpage on the UHasselt website. The action plan will also be published on Zenodo.		
10.	Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research	Data from UHasselt are made accessible via the university's website (repository, who-is-who) and the FRIS platform .	<p>By drawing on evidence-based insights collected via various initiatives, including the forthcoming recommendations of the working group on societal impact, we aim to align our evaluation criteria and tools with international best practices in research assessment (see also Commitment 1 and 2).</p> <p>ECOOM-UHasselt is actively managing the semantics of crucial research data indicators and classification lists. This ensures the consistency and quality of data related to publications, scientific disciplines, funding, and technology domains.</p> <p>Additionally, international developments in the field of research assessment are</p>	<p>Everyone involved in the development of evaluation criteria and tools</p> <p>ECOOM, Information management and strategic data analysis Unit, Directorate OBI</p>	continuous

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			continuously monitored to ensure ongoing alignment with global standards.		